

THE EFFECTS OF ARCS MOTIVATIONAL MODEL ON STUDENT MOTIVATION TO LEARN ENGLISH

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Abstract:

The present study was designed to examine the effects of ARCS motivational model (Keller, 2010) on university prep class students' motivation. For this purpose, ARCS motivational model strategies were inserted to the instructional design via detailed lesson plans which were applied throughout ten weeks. To find out the effects of ARCS model Course Interest Survey (CIS) and Instructional Materials Motivation Survey (IMMS) were administered at the beginning and end of the study. The results of CIS indicated a significant increase since students showed higher course motivation based on the overall CIS results at the end of the study. CIS was evaluated in terms of each ARCS category and a significant difference was observed in all scales. The results showed that the ARCS model inserted language instruction had positive influence on students' course motivation in all categories. As for IMMS results a significant difference in students' instructional motivation scores was found. For a deeper understanding, two subscales of IMMS were assessed separately and the results revealed significant differences in both subscales. Students' instructional materials motivation increased.

Keywords: motivation; motivational model; ARCS; CIS; IMMS

1. Introduction

One of the most emphasized problems of English language teaching/learning in recent years is motivation. As Dörnyei indicates (2001b), students cannot learn if they cannot be motivated. Motivation takes an important place in most learning theories and has

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long been considered as an indicator of success or failure in completing any complex task (Dörnyei, 2001b; Wongwiwatthanakul and Popovich, 2000).

As for the university prep school context in Turkey, even though students are eager to learn English at the beginning of the school term, towards the end of the term high rates of absenteeism and failure in English courses have proven that there is a problem with language learning at most of the university prep classes all over Turkey (Ozkanal and Arıkan, 2011). Some researchers who investigated students' foreign language learning motivation in Turkey found out that they have only mildly positive attitudes towards language learning (Karahan, 2007; Ozturk, 2012; Temur, 2013). Thus, as most instructors admit, lack of motivation seems to be one of the main problems in Turkey (Genc and Kaya, 2010).

However, in Turkish educational system, motivation isn't emphasized as much as it deserves (Acat and Demiral, 2002; Genc and Kaya, 2010). Traditional English language teaching methods in elementary and high schools in Turkey as in many other countries such as South Korea (Samuel, 2001) have a demotivating effect on students. Students may have come to university with their negative past experiences which are considered as demotivating especially among students who lack motivation (Dincer, 2011; Genc and Kaya, 2010; Selcuk, 2011).

Moreover, students might be overwhelmed by the intensity of the curriculum that they are taught (Karahan, 2007). Instructors follow the same syllabus strictly not to fall behind the schedule, because of this they don't focus on a need analysis and avoid the different needs of each class and student (Ucar, 2009). Repetitive instruction and using same kind of materials excessively make the lessons monotonous.

In addition, some of the instructors believe that motivation is not their concern; it is something that students themselves are responsible for (Keller, 2010). These instructors believe that their duty is to provide qualified instruction and motivation will take care of itself eventually. Thus, instructors are not aware of the effect of their teaching on students' motivation or cannot use situation specific strategies to motivate their students (Top, 2009). However, instructor behavior; materials and instruction can have demotivating effect on students and when students lose their motivation, it gets difficult for them to learn (Dörnyei, 2001b; Keller, 2010).

As for the context of this research, the preparatory school students start learning English with an enthusiasm and high motivation. In first couple of weeks, they seem eager and attentive. Even though, they have same instructors and materials, they start to lose their motivation gradually. They start not to attend classes, not to participate in classroom activities. Consequently, students cannot achieve the intended proficiency level as other researchers also admit (Karahan, 2007; Ozcalisan, 2012; Temur, 2013; Top, 2009). As the curriculum progresses, they fall behind the schedule and finally give up.

To understand the problems of the students in detail, before conducting a pilot study students were asked to write comments about the problems they encounter learning English. Based on the results of the pilot study outstanding problems are these; students cannot express themselves clearly in English and they cannot talk efficiently, they have difficulty in learning and remembering vocabulary, they don't know how to learn and they fear not to be able to learn, and they don't like to be criticized in front of others. This shows us that students need an atmosphere that they are encouraged to learn. They should have confidence in themselves to be able to be motivated to learn English. Also, materials should be revised in a way that can attract students' attention, and be related to their own lives. Students also need an instructor who can share the responsibility, understand the needs and problems of the students and act accordingly.

As a result, it is detected that there is a need to increase the motivation of the students. In an attempt to find a way or a model to increase motivation of the students we have decided to apply Keller's ARCS motivational model. The ARCS motivational model, which consists of four categories, Attention, Relevance, Confidence and Satisfaction covers most of the areas of research on human motivation, and is a motivational design process that is compatible with typical instructional design models. The ARCS model is considered to be successful because it doesn't allow traditional teaching system, but it covers different aspects of teaching and accounts for students' perspectives and allows students participate actively based on a need analysis. Based on such a problem analysis it provides motivational strategies to make instruction responsive to the interests and needs of students. The model helps an instructor to get out of the standard routine by still following the syllabus, identify the component of instruction that is problematic and decreases students' motivation to learn, and provide opportunities to motivate their students (Keller, 2010).

Furthermore, for instructors who are eager to motivate their students but have difficulties to put their theoretical knowledge into practice, the ARCS model provides a systematic, easy to follow design that every instructor can implement to motivate students to learn (Keller, 2010). Keller (1983) indicates that by using ARCS motivational model, an educator can create or change the learning conditions/environment in a way that individual students can motivate themselves.

It is thought that ARCS, which approaches the motivation problem from both students' and instructor's point of view, could be applicable in this study. Therefore, this study inserts this model into English language classes at the preparatory school of a state university to find out the effectiveness of the model in language teaching in Turkish context and due to the results to suggest some techniques to increase motivation in language classes.

1.1 ARCS

The ARCS model of motivational design (Keller, 1987a, 1987b) provides a systematic, ten-step approach to insert motivational tactics into instruction.

Table 1: Ten steps

1. Obtain course information
2. Obtain audience information
3. Analyze audience motivation
4. Analyze existing materials and conditions.
5. List objectives and assessments
6. List potential tactics
7. Select and /or design tactics
8. Integrate with instruction
9. Select and develop materials
10. Evaluate and revise

During this ten-step process, the model helps the instructors to create motivational objectives and measurements. Moreover, it provides guidance for creating and selecting motivational tactics, and follows a process that integrates well with instructional design and development. The analysis of motivational needs and corresponding selection of tactics are based on four categories of motivation.

The ARCS model's four categories represent sets of conditions that are necessary for students to be fully motivated, and each of these four categories has subcategories and strategies, that represent specific aspects of motivation.

To motivate students first we need to gain their **Attention**. Tactics for this category can range from simple unexpected events (e.g. a loud whistle, an upside-down word in a visual) to mentally stimulating problems that engage a deeper level of curiosity, especially when presented at the beginning of a lesson. Another important element is variation because people like a certain amount of variety and they will lose interest if your teaching strategies, even the good ones, never change.

The second category is to build **Relevance**. Relevance means connecting the content of instruction to important goals of the learners, their past interests, and their learning styles. Relating instructional content to the learners' future job or academic requirements is an effective way to enhance relevance. Using simulations, analogies, case studies, and examples related to the students' immediate and current interests and experiences are other alternatives.

The third category of the ARCS motivational model is **Confidence**. Instructors should help students to establish a positive expectancy for success. By making the

objectives clear and providing examples of achievements, it is easier to build confidence. Another aspect of confidence is that instructors encourage students to believe that they can achieve any complex task by taking time and by sparing no effort and students should be encouraged to attribute their success or failures to personal effort.

If the learners are curious, interested in the content, and moderately challenged, then they will be motivated to learn. To be able to sustain students' motivation is also important and this purpose is fulfilled by the fourth condition of motivation that is **Satisfaction**. Satisfaction means that students should have positive feelings about their accomplishments and learning experiences. They need to receive recognition and evidence of success that supports their intrinsic feelings of satisfaction and they believe they have been treated fairly. Tangible extrinsic rewards and opportunities to apply newly learned skills support intrinsic feelings of satisfaction. Finally, a sense of equity, or fairness, is another necessity to maintain student motivation.

Therefore, the purpose of this study is to investigate the effects of ARCS based English language instruction on student motivation. Thus, we aim to answer the following research questions:

RQ1.

Do ARCS model based language lessons have effect on students' course motivation?

- a) is there a significant difference in overall motivation scores at the beginning and at the end of the study
- b) b is there a significant difference in ARCS categories- Attention/ Relevance/ Confidence/ Satisfaction scores

RQ2.

Do ARCS model based instructional materials have effect on students' instructional materials' motivation?

- a) is there a significant difference in overall motivation scores at the beginning and at the end of the study
- b) b is there a significant difference in ARCS categories- Attention- Relevance/ Confidence- Satisfaction scores

2. Methodology

To achieve the purpose of the study a mixed method design was carried out. For the quantitative part a pre-post test design was carried out. Lesson plans which were prepared according to ARCS motivational model principles and strategies were applied every Lesson plans which were prepared according to ARCS motivational model

principles and strategies were applied for 10 weeks. For the qualitative part to examine the effectiveness of the model in depth, students were asked to write weekly comments at the end of each week.

2.1 Participants

The present study was conducted using a convenience sample of 30 students. The participants were English preparatory school students at a state university in X University, Turkey, ages between 17-19. The participant group consisted of two classes. Each class had 15 students. The researcher was the class instructor herself.

2.2 Procedure

The instructor had 10 hours of English lesson with each class which provides the instructor sufficient time to implement the ARCS motivational lesson plans (see Appendix for an example lesson plan) and to observe motivational changes. For applying ARCS motivational model, the steps described in the model were followed. First of all, the course information was obtained (Step 1). Since the instructor has been teaching similar courses at preparatory school, she was familiar with the course requirements. General information (age/language level) about the students was gathered through the school administration form and the information about their reason to learn English and their interests were gathered through the classroom interaction. Thus, the audience information was obtained and analyzed (Step 2 and 3).

Besides, course materials were analyzed in line with course objectives. Some materials were replaced and some of them were adapted. Objectives of the course and curriculum requirements were considered and lesson objectives were inserted to the lesson plans (Step 4 and 5). ARCS strategies list was reviewed and potential tactics were listed (Step 6). Strategies that can be used to cover course objectives and materials were selected and integrated to the lesson plans where necessary so that instruction was presented in a way that could motivate students. (Step 7 and 8). If additional materials were needed to support the strategies, they were provided (Step 9). After application of the lesson plans, strategies checklist was reviewed and strategies were checked to see if they were applied successfully (Step 10).

The data were collected during 2012-2013 academic year spring semester. All participants received the same motivational instruction and were administered two scales prepared by Keller to measure the level of student motivation both at the beginning, and at the end of the application. In the first lesson of the semester, the participants were administered Course Interest Survey (CIS) and Instructional Materials Motivation Survey (IMMS). Students were asked to evaluate the first term in terms of the instruction materials used in class using IMMS, and evaluate the course in terms of

applications and instructor behavior using CIS. The IMMS and CIS were also given to the students at the end of the 10 weeks application to be able to recognize the difference in participants' motivation. The results obtained from the scales were analyzed using quantitative methods. Moreover, students were asked to write comments related to the instruction and materials used on the last lesson of each week to support the quantitative data.

2.3 Research Tools

The Instructional Materials Motivation Survey (IMMS) was developed by Keller as a data collection tool to test the effectiveness of implementation of the ARCS strategies in different contexts. The IMMS measures student motivation towards specific instructional materials. The IMMS originally consists of 36-item survey with a Likert-type scale (Keller, 2010) and has four categories (Attention, Relevance, Confidence, and Satisfaction). The response scale ranges from 1 (Not True) to 5 (Very True).

In this study, Turkish versions of the questionnaires were used. The Turkish version of the IMMS was taken from Kutu and Sozbilir's (2011) study. The Turkish version of the survey consists of 24 items with two factors. The first factor is Attention-Relevance and the second factor is Confidence-Satisfaction.

Table 2: The reliability coefficient (Cronbach's Alpha) of IMMS

	Kutu and Sozbilir's study	Pilot study	Actual study
Total	0,83	0,88	0,87
Attention-Relevance	0,79	0,89	0,76
Confidence-Satisfaction	0,69	0,84	0,84

The Course Interest Survey (CIS) was designed to measure students' motivation towards classroom instruction by Keller (2010). The survey consists of four categories (Attention, Relevance, Confidence, Satisfaction). The Turkish version of CIS was taken from Varank's (2003) study. Turkish version consists of 24 items with two factors: Attention- Relevance, Confidence-Satisfaction.

Table 3: The reliability coefficient (Cronbach's Alpha) of CIS

	Varank's study	Pilot study	Actual study
Total	0,95	0,83	0,87
Attention	0,84	0,56	0,65
Relevance	0,84	0,67	0,65
Confidence	0,81	0,69	0,67
Satisfaction	0,88	0,61	0,72

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Students' Classroom Instruction Motivation

The statistical data for Course Interest Survey are displayed in Table 3. The findings revealed that there is a statistically significant difference between pre-application ($M=3.29$, $SD=.256$) and post-application ($M=4.15$, $SD=.413$) scores with regard to students' reactions to classroom instruction ($t(29)= -9.707$, $p<.001$). Thus, statistical results of CIS show that the ARCS strategies had positive influence since students showed higher motivation based on the overall CIS results at the end of the study.

Table 4: CIS Paired Samples Test

CI	N	M	SD	SE	df	t	Sig (2-tailed)
Pre-application	30	3.29	.256	.047	29	-9.707	.000*
Post- application	30	4.15	.413	.075			

* $p<.001$

The model has been applied and found effective by many researchers in online settings in teaching several courses such as language, computer, archeology etc. (Carpenter, 2011; Colakoglu, 2009; Gabrielle, 2003; Huett, Kalinowski, Moller and Huett,2008; Keller, Deiman, and Liu, 2005; Robb, 2010) and face to face settings in teaching courses such as psychology, science and math (Balantekin, 2014; Cengiz, 2009; Kutu, 2011; Naime-Diefenbach, 1991; Visser, 1990; Visser and Keller, 1990) and the present study supports the effectiveness of the model in face to face language settings.

The results may be affected by the fact that the instructor who applies the model was reported to be caring and enthusiastic and these instructor characteristics contribute to the effectiveness of the model in enhancing students' motivation (Robb, 2010). Studies conducted on effect of teacher behavior on students' motivation in Turkey also show that friendly and enthusiastic instructors, and instructors who create a relaxing atmosphere for students to share their ideas are highly motivating (Kahraman, 2014; Partlak, 2014).

In the present study, at the end of first week, the researcher sent a motivational text message to every student. During critical periods (first week, before midterm, after midterm, through the end of the semester) researcher send other text messages to keep students alert and motivated. Moreover, the researcher constantly observed student behaviors in class, wrote motivational messages for individual students, and delivered them in class. Moreover, students received extra materials and reminders via e-mails. Sending text messages and e-mails as motivating attempts helped establish a relation

between the instructor and the students and proved to be effective as in the studies investigated the effects of motivational messages (Huett, Kalinowski, Moller and Huett, 2008; Robb, 2010).

Moreover, the model was applied for such a long period of time that change in students' motivation could be observed. Unlike Moller (1993) who applied confidence strategies only for a short period of time and couldn't get significant results, in this study the model was applied for ten weeks inserting all the strategies which provided enough time to apply the model successfully and to see the effects of it and enabled the instructor observe changes.

Applying a pilot study was also an important factor which contributed to the success of the application. Keller (2010) suggests trying out the strategies before implementing them and in order to improve the quality and efficacy of the actual study implementing a pilot study is beneficial.

The ARCS model is successful because it raises the awareness of the instructor to involve the students and decrease the usage of traditional teaching system where only the instructor is active and students are just passive listeners in class, but it covers different aspects of teaching and allows students participate actively, so the model was a challenge for the students in this study. That is, the instructor was willing to share the floor with the students, which is one of main factors in the model and which is considered to increase motivation (Kahraman 2014).

The CIS can also be scored for each of the four categories. Thus, to analyze the results obtained through the scale in detail each ARCS category was evaluated separately to see if there was a significant difference in mean scores and whether the strategies of each category was successfully applied into the classroom instruction.

Table 5: CIS Paired Samples T-test for all subscales

CIS	PRE-APPLICATION		POST-APPLICATION		df	t	p
	M	SD	M	SD			
Attention	3.00	.472	4.19	.494	29	-11.310	.000*
Relevance	3.58	.468	4.23	.484	29	-4.870	.000*
Confidence	3.42	.362	4.16	.448	29	-6.897	.000*
Satisfaction	3.13	.461	4.02	.516	29	-6.579	.000*

*p<.001

The greatest increase was seen in *Attention* subscale, since motivating students starts with getting their attention and maintaining it. Using strategies such as stating objectives of each lesson, playing short videos, songs, visuals and role-play activities improves students' attention to the lesson and students show more interest in the

language items when some unusual, surprising things are designed. (Lin, 2008; McConnell, Hoover and Sassed, 2001).

Students' weekly comments support the statistical data. Materials and activities were perceived as interesting and gained students' attention. Supporting topics with visuals helped students to clarify the meaning easily and to understand the topic better (Wall, Higgins and Smith, 2005). For example, vocabulary power point presentations were used to introduce new vocabulary or picture of a customer and a waiter was used to show how to order at a restaurant and students' curiosity was aroused when these kinds of materials were used.

Another positive comment that proves the effectiveness of the model regarding to Attention category is the instructor's teaching style. Instructor's professional knowledge/ skills and classroom management style were suggested to be motivating by Dörnyei (2001a) and Wlodkowski (1993). To give an example; as stated by one of the students, the activity in which the instructor showed coins, credit cards and notes from her purse to teach money related vocabulary helped students focus their attention on the lesson.

The results related to *Relevance* category indicate a significant difference between pre and post application scores. It can be concluded that Relevance strategies are effective in motivating students as supported by literature (Chang, 2001; Chang and Lehman, 2002; Monk, 2009).

With respect to relevance category, important points were emphasized and the objectives of the activities were explained so that students understood the importance, relevance of a task. It was reported by the students that they could establish connections between their lives and the instruction, activities matched with their personal goals and all the activities conducted in class were fruitful for them. For instance, students who were planning to participate in Work and Travel or Erasmus programs paid close attention to topics such as asking/giving directions, ordering at a restaurant, making suggestions. Thus, topics and tasks relevant to students' interests and lives were highly motivating relevant strategies as also supported by literature (Kahraman, 2014; Partlak, 2014).

In this study, personal language was used to make learners feel they were cared (Chang, 2001; Chang and Lehman, 2002). Thus, the students received individual attention and their ideas were taken into account which increased their motivation because students want to feel included and be a part of decision-making process (Arnold and Brown, 1999; Dörnyei, 2001a).

As for the third sub-category, *Confidence*, students' confidence related to course also increased. Literature indicates that students' confidence to learn English can be stimulated by confidence strategies (Huett, 2006; Lin, 2008).

In terms of confidence, it was also obvious from students' comments that they gradually became more and more confident with their English. Students stated they felt that they were really learning something, they were expanding their knowledge after each lesson, they could understand better and this gave them confidence to learn English. In addition, students preferred pair work activities and there are studies revealing that pair work is less threatening (Wajnryb, 1992; Zuniga, 2010). So we made use of pair work which could have increased students' confidence (Carpenter, 2011; Johnson, 2012; Lin, 2008).

What's more students were also asked to include suggestions how to improve instruction and materials which seemed to be effective. They commented that they felt pleased and involved when their demands were met. For instance, some students commented that they needed more listening exercises and the instructor provided extra listening activities. Recognizing individual students' efforts to learn and making students believe that their instructor has high expectations that students can achieve are motivating (Kahraman, 2014; Partlak, 2014). Students want to be an active participant of the process (Arnold and Brown, 1999; Dörnyei, 2001a). Another confidence strategy that increased students' motivation was giving corrective and positive feedback since feedback generates energy that students use constructively in class when given appropriately (Carpenter, 2011, Johnson, 2012).

As in all other categories, students who participated in this study showed positive reaction in terms of *Satisfaction*. With regard to satisfaction, category students felt satisfied with the instruction since they believed that it would be beneficial for them in the future and made a remark that they were excited to apply the skills they acquired. Students reported that they felt satisfied because they were praised by the instructor. According to Partlak's study (2014), praising students for their participation is motivating. The students also commented that they enjoyed their learning experience, they learned, their progress was recognized by the instructor, and they worked with friends and shared ideas with each other (Lin, 2008).

Moreover, games with scoring systems were included to provide extrinsic rewards to reinforce intrinsically interesting tasks. When students play games they enjoy themselves and learn at the same time (Paras and Bizzocchi, 2005; Partlak, 2014). For instance, one of the students commented that she liked vocabulary games best since she easily remembered the words they used to play the game.

It can be said that these strategies are effective in enhancing student satisfaction.

3.2 Students' Instructional Materials Motivation

The findings indicated that there was a statistically significant difference between pre-application ($M=3.40$, $SD=.516$) and post-application ($M=4.37$, $SD=.387$) scores in terms of

students' motivation level ($t(29) = -8.081, p < .001$) (See Table 4). Post-application results indicated higher student motivation.

Table 6: IMMS Paired Samples Test

IMMS	M	N	SD	SE	df	t	Sig (2-tailed)
Pre-application	3.40	30	.516	.094	29	-8.081	.000*
Post application	4.37	30	.387	.071			

* $p < .001$

Instructional materials prepared in line with ARCS strategies were found effective in motivating students in terms of course materials in teaching several online and face to face courses such as science, psychology, management etc. (Gabrielle, 2003; Naime-Diefenbach 1991; Nwagbara, 1993; Song, 1998; Song and Keller, 2001). Gabrielle (2003), Song (1998) and Song and Keller (2001) integrated ARCS strategies to motivate students in online science courses, as a result students' instructional materials motivation increased. Naime-Diefenbach (1991) made use of Attention and Confidence strategies in a face to face psychology course and these strategies increased students' attention to the instructional materials and Nwagbara (1993) inserted Relevance strategies to the instructional materials in an online management course and students' instructional materials motivation increased. The current study results prove the effectiveness of instructional materials prepared in line with ARCS strategies in face to face language classes.

The effectiveness of the ARCS strategies inserted to instructional materials can be explained by following factors. Systematically designed instructional strategies can positively affect student motivation (Gabrielle, 2003) and students appreciate the efforts of instructor while preparing the material. Thus, using variety of materials increases students' interest to the lesson (Naime-Diefenbach 1991).

Table 7: IMMS Paired Samples T-test for all subscales

IMMS	PRE-APPLICATION		POST-APPLICATION		df	t	p
	M	SD	M	SD			
Attention/ Relevance	3.44	.664	4.50	.375	29	-7.686	.000*
Confidence/ Satisfaction	3.37	.556	4.27	.485	29	-6.365	.000*

* $p < .001$

The IMMS was also scored for each factor. Paired-samples t-test result revealed a statistically significant difference between pre-application mean scores and post-application mean scores in both categories. Students' showed positive reactions to the instructional materials based on ARCS strategies. Thus, it can be concluded that materials prepared based on ARCS strategies were effective in improving student motivation in terms of Attention- Relevance and Confidence-Satisfaction as Gabrielle (2003) and Kutu and Sozbilir, (2011) also reported.

Students' comments also proved the effectiveness of the materials. Students reported that materials helped them pay attention and get interested in the lesson; they were consistent and relevant with the objectives, materials aroused the feeling of success and made students feel confident; and students were pleased with the materials and satisfied.

To illustrate, when introducing the topic "describing a city", instructor provided pictures of 12 famous cities around the world and in pairs asked students to write the city names. The pair which gave most correct answers got tokens. This activity and materials of the activity were considered to be highly enjoyable because pictures were used to gain students' attention, showing city pictures were relevant to the objectives, and famous cities were chosen so that every student could name some of them and felt confident, they worked in pairs which increased their chance of guessing more cities and this prompted feeling of satisfaction.

Attention-Relevant strategies implemented to the instructional materials improved students' attention and willingness to participate and complete activities (Chang and Lehman, 2002; Means, Jonassen and Dwyer, 1997; Naime-Diffenbach, 1991; Nwagbara, 1993; Song, 1998).

Attention strategies such as engaging the students' interest by using feedback interaction that requires active thinking, presenting problem-solving situations in a context, using visual enhancements to support instruction, are effective strategies that enhance students' attention in the lesson (Song and Keller, 2001; Sozbilir and Kutu, 2011)

The results revealed the effectiveness of Relevance strategies in motivating students and support literature and some other research findings that students are more eager to participate in instructional materials that they perceive as relevant and helpful accomplishing their personal goals (Chang and Lehman, 2002; Nwagbara, 1993).

Materials prepared using Confidence and Satisfaction strategies increased students Confidence and Satisfaction as Huett also found out (2006). Clear and easy- to-follow materials were used to make them feel comfortable and confident since overly difficult materials demotivate students as Johnson (2012) suggests. Students were also given opportunities to give and receive feedback for each task. The confidence and

satisfaction strategies contributed to the success of the study and were reported as effective since students became more committed to the learning tasks and realized higher academic goals and this type of confidence and satisfaction contributes to ongoing motivation or the feeling that students want to continue learning English. The results of the study indicated that novelty, materials with appropriate level but challenging, materials supported with visuals, feedback promote feeling of confidence and satisfaction.

4. Conclusion and Pedagogical Implications

The current study has supported the idea of adaptability and effectiveness of the ARCS motivational model in an English language class. Though the results of the study cannot be generalized, they indicate some implications related to language teaching. This study indicates that students' motivation to learn can be increased applying ARCS motivational design since students experience a positive and motivating language learning atmosphere.

The effectiveness of ARCS motivational model both on students' course interest and instructional materials motivation might be explained by the fact that the strategies are presented in a very clear way that instructors can apply them in their own settings easily. As long as instructors analyze their audience and materials carefully, and adapt the model according to their own objectives and teaching/learning context, the chance of model to be effective is high (Keller, 2010). In this study, model was successfully implemented and strategies were used appropriately, thus student motivation increased. Strategies were identified and they were systematically implemented to the course instruction or materials via detailed lesson plans which provides a plan of work and guidance for the instructor. As a consequence of these applications, the model was effective in preparatory classes.

The four categories of ARCS motivational model exert impacts on students' motivational level. The strategies that belong to these four categories are proved to be essential elements in the process of teaching and learning English. Students' initial concerns related to learning English were minimized using ARCS strategies.

The students' Attention to learn English has been gained and maintained with the attention strategies such as stating objectives of each lesson, playing songs and games, visuals, role-plays and providing variety. We can conclude that the key point is to be aware of the fact that getting students' attention to the lesson is the first step to motivate students since attention strategies help students focus their attention on the lesson and stay concentrated. Thus, the fear of not being able to learn, which was a mentioned problem at the beginning of the study, was eliminated.

Course content Relevance in learning English has been improved by combining course instruction with students' past experiences and existing knowledge, emphasizing the present value and future usefulness of the instruction, providing choice, answering students' question why they are learning a particular subject. Relating materials students' own lives and using variety also helped them to learn and remember vocabulary better which was a mentioned problem.

In addition, students felt confidence in English by providing self-evaluating tools, attributing success to effort, providing low risk conditions to encourage students to participate and helping students build positive expectations for success. Initially, students commented that being criticized about mistakes in front of others is demotivating. It can be concluded from the results of this study that when instructors listen to the students attentively without interrupting, and show interest and reflect on their ideas instead of focusing on only their mistakes, they become confident about their English level.

The students' level of satisfaction with their learning process has been improved through strategies such as providing constructive feedback, rewards, avoiding threats, frequent positive instructor and student communication. These satisfaction strategies helped students to overcome the problem that they don't know how to learn. It is important that students leave the class with positive feelings. In this study students' hard work and efforts were appreciated, they were treated fairly and built good relationships with the instructor. At the end of the study, they commented that they could talk better English which was another problem at the beginning.

Moreover, the results of the study may help us to draw conclusions and implications for the English instructors, course book writers and instructor trainers. First implication that can be drawn from the present study is that instructor should review lesson materials and choose the suitable ones, prepare clear, interesting, and applicable materials, relevant for the students and appropriate for their level to gain and sustain student motivation. Because, some course books that instructors rely on do not include motivational materials. If instructors carefully evaluate materials before they bring them to class, they can easily overcome these problems. This implies that instructors should be aware of the fact that they play a crucial role on student motivation and should feel responsible.

In addition, following course book extensively can become boring because after a period of time it starts to be monotonous and students lose their attention to the lesson. Providing similar activities especially cut-up, matching, info-gap activities makes them more enthusiastic and energetic and brings variety to the instruction, since course books can be boring and instructors may need extra materials to support the book (Selcuk, 2011; Tomlinson, 2012; Tze-Ming, Chou,2010). Course books shouldn't be considered as

the only teaching tool (Fredericks 2005). New and interesting materials and visuals are needed to maintain students attention as also Acat and Demiral (2002) suggested.

Another implication is that, instructors should encourage students that they can achieve on the condition they put enough effort and examples of successful people should be mentioned so that students believe in their capabilities.

There are also implications for Course book writers. Course book designers should consider motivational characteristics of their target audience and take them into consideration while designing course books. Moreover, motivational tactics and strategies can be inserted to the course books and additional suggestions can be provided for the instructors.

One implication of this study is related to instructor training. It should be underlined that motivation is not something that only students themselves are responsible for. Thus, in instructor education and education policies of government, motivation should be considered as an important factor and the importance of motivation should be emphasized more.

The effectiveness of the ARCS model can be examined in different settings, with different age and proficiency level groups. The participants of this study were pre-intermediate level students. Different proficiency levels may react to ARCS motivational model differently. The model can be applied to different proficiency levels and the differences can be observed. Finally, course books or instructional materials in terms of ARCS strategies can be evaluated. A course books' motivational effectiveness can be identified and suggestions can be made.

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Appendix

EXAMPLE LESSON PLAN

<p>Course Title: Main Course Speak-out pre-intermediate Class: prep- 5 and 8 Time required: 3 lessons</p>	<p>Materials: course book, course book interactive programme, pictures, extra photocopies</p>
<p>Unit title: UNIT 7- CHANGES Unit objectives: Throughout this unit, the student will be able to achieve the following aims:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To talk about a life change. • To tell the story of a man’s life. • To find specific information about facilities • To read and predict information in a story. • To use paragraphs to write about a change and to write a blog/diary. 	<p>Lesson title: 7.1 STUCK IN A RUT Lesson objectives: By the end of this lesson students will be able to;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ask and answer questions about pastimes and past activities. • Describe past activities and personal experiences. • Talk about changes in their lives.
<p>Instructional tactics</p>	<p>Motivational tactics (ARCS)</p>
<p>Teacher explains the objectives and importance of the lesson clearly. (Today, we will talk about famous people and big changes they made in their lives and we will talk about changes in our lives mentioning our childhood. Etc.)</p>	<p>State explicitly how the instruction builds on the learner’s existing skills. (R) Incorporate clearly stated, appealing learning goals into instruction (C)</p>
<p>1A Teacher shows pictures of three famous people who experienced a big life change. Ask a series of questions about these people. (ex. Do you know that Lady Gaga was a waitress before she became famous?) Discuss about these people’s life changing experience. (Teacher uses the target structure ‘used to’ during the discussion) Teacher asks sts whether they would like to change their lives or not and gets answers from some sts. Shows interest to sts answers.</p>	<p>Show visual representation of an important object, vary the format of instruction, introduce a fact that seems to contradict the learner’s past experience (A) Use personal language and get some personal information from sts (R)</p>
<p>1B T. tells sts that there are a lot of people who change their lives. Because they are not famous we don’t know them. We are going to listen to a radio programme about two women who changed their lives. Before listening to the programme let’s read the introduction of this program. There are some unknown phrases, please do not use a dictionary. We will try to understand them from the context together. T. and Sts. talk about the radio program.</p>	<p>Provide clear instruction (C) Provide meaningful alternative methods for accomplishing a goal (S)</p>
<p>2A using contextual clues t and sts try to guess the words together and sts uses these new phrases in a fill in the blanks</p>	<p>Verbally reinforce a student’s intrinsic pride in accomplishing a task (S)</p>

activity. T. emphasizes that sts don't always need a dictionary.	Include statements about the likelihood of success with effort (C)
3A We have learned these phrases since they use some of them in the listening text. We are going to listen about Jasmin and Anita. Look at their pictures, what do you think they have changed in their lives? (T. writes on board sts guesses) 3B. sts listen and check their predictions.	Use content related examples (A)
6A We know the old jasmine and the new one. Let's look at changes. (sts gives the information and teacher writes them on board using "used to") Old She used to work in a hospital. She is a musician now. She didn't use to have free time. She has a lot of free time. (T. and sts examine the example sentence and talk about uses of "used to") Sts complete grammar activities.	Vary the format of instruction (A)
5A We have learned a lot about the lives of jasmine and anita. Do you think they made the right decisions about their lives? Would you make any changes like this? Who would?	
7A not big as Anita and Jasmin's but we have also made changes in our lives. There are some possible changes, which of them also true for you. Share with your partner do you have any similarities?	Shift between teacher-student instruction and student- student interface (A) Use activities that require learner participation (A)
8A make a list of four changes in your lives. (appearance, home, work, hobbies etc.) work in groups of four, who changed the most. T. asks the groups about who changed most and what the changes are.	Have sts learn new skill under low risk conditions, but practice performance of well-learned tasks under realistic conditions (c)
9A there is another life change example, Ryan. But he wrote his experience for a magazine. Lets read it and find out the big change. (T. and sts together go through the paragraph) 9C Imagine that you are working for a magazine. Your editor wants you to write about a life-changing experience like Ryan's. Search on the internet and write a similar paragraph we will read them tomorrow. HOMEWORK	Organize materials on an increasing level of difficulty, (c)

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